

Is the mystery of the masses of elementary particles solved?

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Abstract

An explanation of the masses of baryons and mesons is still one of the great unsolved mysteries of physics and poses a significant challenge for our time. In this paper, a novel approach is presented that could shed light on this issue by proposing a new form of energy that has not been considered to date. By accounting for this new energy form, the masses of the elementary particles will likely become explainable. In addition, this new form of energy also sheds light on the spectroscopy of mesons and baryons. The several observed energy levels of mesons and baryons, which have not been explained thus far, become more understandable when considering this new energy form.

Abstrait

Le secret des masses des particules élémentaires est-il percé ? Expliquer les masses des baryons et des mésons demeure l'une des énigmes non élucidées de la physique contemporaine et constitue un défi de taille pour notre époque. Le présent article développe une approche novatrice qui pourrait faire la lumière sur ce thème en s'intéressant à une nouvelle énergie jusqu'alors non considérée. En s'appuyant sur cette nouvelle forme d'énergie, il devient vraisemblablement possible d'expliquer les masses des particules élémentaires. Par ailleurs, cette nouvelle forme d'énergie jette également un jour nouveau sur la spectroscopie des mésons et des baryons. Les différents niveaux d'énergie observés sur les mésons et les baryons, que l'on ne parvenait pas non plus à comprendre jusqu'à aujourd'hui, peuvent être expliqués si l'on considère cette nouvelle forme d'énergie.

I. Introduction

The masses of mesons and baryons are still difficult to describe theoretically, and different methods to accomplish this task have been developed in the last decades. The simplest method uses current masses and constituent quark masses; thus, the constituent quark masses are simply amounts that can be added when forming a meson or baryon, and the resulting mass is a first approximation of the mass of the resulting meson or baryon. Using this model, the binding energy, which is the largest component of the mass of a baryon or meson, is equally distributed between the constituent quarks. However, in the following, only the original rest mass of the quarks is used. This original quark mass is also called the current quark mass. In more complex models, the spin and isospin energies are considered as additional summands. It is important to consider these energies for an adequate description of vector-mesons and the excited states of pseudo-scalar mesons and vector-mesons. In this work, a much more detailed model is presented. In this novel model, in addition to the sum of the constituent quark masses and the spin and isospin energies, the quark potential is also considered according to quantum chromodynamics (QCD), and a new energy form, the mass-charge binding energy, is proposed.

According to an earlier theory of the author, a previously unknown interaction between mass and charge exists¹.

The theory is described in further detail in the March 2013 issue of the journal *Physics Essays*¹. In short, the so-called mass-charge binding energy is a new energy form that emerges if a charge interacts with a mass and is analogous to the well-known charge-charge energy (Coulomb potential) and mass-mass energy (Newtonian gravity). This new energy is determined by multiplying the same physical structure's mass by the charge and then dividing by their distance. The so-called "mass-charge binding energy," as described in the *Physics Essays* paper, results in another previously unrecognized additional mass defect in the calculation of the masses of elementary particles.

Because the new mass-charge force always works in an attractive direction, the sign of the charges involved is irrelevant. Therefore, in the case of elementary particles, the total magnitude of the absolute charges must be considered for calculating the mass-charge binding energy. It thus becomes apparent that the charged particle form does not always have the smaller mass; but however, the particle form which carries more charges in absolute amounts at the quark level, has the larger mass defect and subsequently has the smaller mass.

If we examine the D-meson as an example, the D-zero (cu) particle carries more elementary charges ($4/3e$) at the molecular quark level than the D-plus (cd) or the D-minus (dc) particle (both $1e$). Therefore, more mass-charge binding energy is released for the D-zero particle, and a smaller total particle mass results for the D-zero particle compared with the D-plus or D-minus particle.

Considering the resulting additional mass defect, it becomes apparent that the up quark and the down quark could also be the same particle. The mass difference between these two particles then results from the greater magnitude of charge carried by the up quark. However, in the substitution of a down quark by an up quark, the total amount of charge in the resulting particle increases by $1/3e$. This increase leads to a higher mass-charge binding energy being released and, accordingly, to an additional previously unconsidered mass defect. Thus, according to their molecular quark composition, the higher charged elementary particles have a lower mass than the corresponding less-charged elementary particles.

To determine the mass of an elementary particle, the following components must be considered:

- The spin of the quarks: particles with a spin of $-1/2$ have approximately 300 MeV less mass than particles with a spin of $3/2$.
- The molecular constitution of the elementary particles in the quarks: the resulting mass as a sum of the masses of the constitution quarks must be calculated.
- The new mass-charge binding energy, which decreases the total energy and hence the total mass of the resulting particle. This energy is calculated from a product of the total amount of charge and the total current masses (molecular sum) of the quarks in the particle divided by the particle radius r .
- The quark potential, which consists of two parts: one part is negative and decreases with increasing radius while the other part grows linearly with increasing radius $(-4a/r+kr)$, as already known.

II. Calculation of Particle Masses

With these simple rules, it should be possible to calculate the mass of an elementary particle as the sum of the masses of the current quarks and the spin energy minus the mass-charge binding energy and the quark potential.

$$m = \sum m_i + \Delta M_{ss} - \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{M|Q|}{r} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} + k \cdot r \quad (1)$$

$$(A) \quad M_{ss}(s = -\frac{3}{2}) = 300MeV; \Delta M_{ss}(s = -\frac{1}{2}) = 0MeV \quad (2)$$

$$m = \sum m_i + \Delta M_{ss} - \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{\sum m_i \sum |q_i|}{r} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} + k \cdot r \quad (3)$$

(B) As an example, given \sum^-, \sum^0, \sum^+ : $r = 2$,

$$\sum^- : dds(1e, 108) : m = 108 - \frac{1}{4} \frac{108 \cdot 1}{r} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} + kr = 1197.4MeV \quad (4)$$

$$\sum^0 : uds(\frac{4}{3}e, 108) : m = 108 - \frac{1}{4} \frac{108 \cdot \frac{4}{3}}{r} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} + kr = 1192.6MeV \quad (5)$$

$$\sum^+ : uus(\frac{5}{3}e, 108) : m = 108 - \frac{1}{4} \frac{108 \cdot \frac{5}{3}}{r} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} + kr = 1189.4MeV \quad (6)$$

(C) As an example, given $n^0, p^+ : r = 1$,

$$n^0 : udd(\frac{4}{3}e, 12) : m = 12 - \frac{1}{4} \frac{12 \cdot \frac{4}{3}}{r} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} + kr = 939.5 MeV \quad (7)$$

$$p^+ : uud(\frac{5}{3}e, 12) : m = 12 - \frac{1}{4} \frac{12 \cdot \frac{5}{3}}{r} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} + kr = 938.2 MeV \quad (8)$$

Formulas **A** (Eq. 1-3): the mass or total energy of an elementary particle (meson, baryon) is given by the sum of the current masses of the quarks, the spin energy, the mass-charge binding energy and the quark potential.

Formulas **B** (Eq. 4-6): Some exemplary sample calculations for calculating the particle masses are provided for sigma particles.

Formulas **C** (Eq. 7,8): Further sample calculations for determining particle masses are provided for the neutron and proton.

III. Description and explanation of the formulas

The formula for calculating the mass of an elementary particle is initially given by the sum of the current masses of the constituent quarks. In addition, a term that is dependent on the spin interaction must be added. One quarter of the mass-charge binding energy, which is reciprocal to the radius r in a manner analogous to the Coulomb potential and the Newtonian gravitational potential, is then subtracted from this result. The quark potential must then be added. The quark potential is known to be composed of two terms: one of $-4/3$ of alpha divided by the radius r and the other of k times the radius r . If the radius of a particle increases, the quark potential also increases; with this growth, energy must be added to the system, and subsequently, the mass of the resulting particle will increase.

Therefore, formulas **A** (Eq. 1-3) provide the overall theoretical formula, while formulas **B** (Eq. 4-6) describes a concrete example, the sigma baryons, and formulas **C** (Eq. 7,8) describes the formula for the case of a proton and neutron.

As observed from these formulas, the radius of the resulting particle is also very important. Different particles, or even different excitation states of a single particle, can result in different radii, even if the quark compositions of these species are identical. It is further assumed that different quarks might possess slightly different radii and that larger quarks possess slightly larger radii. Therefore, the radius will also increase for the meson if heavier quarks are contained within the particle,- baryons are considered to be more stable in radii. The mass-charge binding energy will become more important for particles composed of heavier quarks because this energy is formed by the product of the total amount of charge and the initial mass.

It is assumed here that the radius effect becomes particularly important in the description of heavy mesons because their masses increase if heavy strange and charm quarks are involved in their formation. Thus, the additional mass of the resulting mesons cannot be explained by simply subtracting the current masses of the constituent quarks. An additional effect of mass

generation must be considered. If the radii of the constituent quarks are different and increase for heavier quarks, then, because the quark potential increases linearly with the radius, it becomes clear that the resulting masses of the heavier mesons become even larger than the sum of the constituent quark masses. Therefore, the meson masses extend across a large range from 139 MeV, in the case of pions (mostly current quark mass), to 5279 MeV (a significant amount of binding energy) in the case of B mesons. Compared with mesons, the radius effect is much less important for baryons. The large radius could also be the reason for the small difference between the B⁺ and the B⁰ meson, as the mass-charge binding energy decreases with 1/r and nearly vanishes.

Considering now the very concrete example of a neutron and proton see formulas **C** (Eq.7,8), the neutron has the greater mass compared with the proton mass of approximately 1.3 MeV due to its lower total sum of the absolute amount of charges on its quarks.

If we compare the d->u substitution that occurs between a neutron and proton with the d-> u substitution that occurs between a xi-minus and a xi-zero baryon, it can be observed that the mass difference is 7 MeV for the xi-minus and xi-zero baryon compared with 1.3 MeV for the neutron and proton. This difference is caused by the larger mass of the two strange quarks in the xi baryons. In addition, because the mass-charge binding energy is given by the mass-charge product, the resulting mass difference is larger if the initially interacting current masses of the quarks are larger (as for the xi baryons).

Let us compare the masses of the baryon particles sigma-minus, sigma-zero and sigma-plus observed in formulas **B** (Eq. 4-6). We see that these particles are heavier than nucleons, presumably because they contain strange quarks. Accordingly, the masses of these particles are greater than those of the neutron and the proton; in addition, the quark potential becomes more important here. For the sigma particles, with an increasing amount of absolute charge, the resulting mass again decreases. However, this time, the mass decreases not by 1 MeV as in the case between a neutron and a proton but by 4 MeV. This large decrease arises because the heavier strange quark has a mass of 100 and thus leads to a higher mass-charge binding energy here, which in turn results in a greater mass difference between the resulting particles.

This examination of different special particles indicates that the experimental particle masses correspond well with the values predicted from the theory presented here.

Therefore, the mass-charge binding energy must be calculated by including the sum of the current mass of the constituent quarks multiplied by the sum of the absolute magnitude of the charges of the particle. If we next consider a xi particle and compare it with the sigma particles, the xi particle has a larger mass by approximately 100 MeV. This mass can easily be explained by the additional strange quark, and thus, the mass is approximately the same as that of the sigma particles; however, the xi particles contain a second strange quark. This time, the uncharged particles possess a greater amount of absolute charges than the charged particles because a down quark is replaced by an up quark. This time, the difference is 7 MeV, which corresponds to the doubled mass-charge binding energy, which becomes free here, compared with the sigma particles through the duplicate strange quark presented here, corresponding to twice the mass difference at 200 MeV. Analogous calculations of the masses of other particles should also be performed.

Thus, it is important not to consider the charge q of the whole particle (the "net charge", $\sum q$) when calculating the mass-charge binding energy,- but instead to consider the sum of the absolute amount of charges of the constituent quarks ("molecular quark structure" and the "molecular charge sum" $\sum |q|$).

While the nucleons (protons and neutrons) appear to have a radius of "1", the sigma particle appears to have a slightly larger radius, however later on we will fix the radius and consider a "rest- potential".

Analogous to the classification of baryons, the heavier the quarks of a meson, the greater is the resulting overall mass, and the greater the mass is, the greater the mass-charge binding energy and, thus, the greater the difference in the masses of the resulting particles among differently charged species. In addition, the increasingly larger radii of the heavier quarks must be considered. Accordingly, the D0 meson has a significant difference in mass compared with the D+ and the D meson. This predicted mass difference can be clearly observed for the corresponding 2400 MeV particles (D0 2318 MeV, D+ 2403 MeV, D 85 MeV), while the masses of the basal D particles and several other particles could not be adequately determined experimentally according to the data of the Particle Data Group². Therefore, only "averaged" data are provided for the D0 particle, at 1864 MeV, and for several other particles. However, the mass difference between differently charged species of one particle appears to be much smaller for D- mesons in the ground state compared with D(2400) mesons in an excited state.

Therefore, the model provided here for the description of meson and baryon masses results in new insights into the mass schema.

We now examine some additional special particles:

If we examine the meson masses of a Bs0 meson consisting of an s and a b quark, this meson has a mass of 5366 MeV, and if we compare it with the mass of the Bc+ meson consisting of a c and a b quark with a mass of only 6277 MeV, the mass difference between these two mesons is only approximately 1 GeV. However, because of the additional s quark, the mass difference should be approximately 1.17 GeV. In addition, the total amount of charge increases from 2/3e for the Bs0 meson to 1e for the Bc+ meson. Therefore, it can be demonstrated that the smaller-than-expected mass difference is caused by the larger mass-charge binding energy and the larger mass defect in the case of the higher charged Bc+-meson.

A similar mass reduction can be observed if we compare the sigma-zero particle (uds) with the lambda-charm-plus particle (udc). This comparison represents a strange-to-charm substitution. The charm quark has approximately 1100 MeV more current mass than the strange quark; however, it also has 1/3 more charge than the strange quark. Therefore, the resulting lambda-charm-plus particle does not have 1100 MeV more mass than the sigma-zero particle but, instead, approximately 1090 MeV more mass.

IV. Excited particle status

For mesons, the mass-charge binding energy becomes particularly important if we examine the excited particle states. The more strongly the meson is excited, the greater the resulting mass-charge binding energy.

In some forms of excitation of a meson, the distance between the quarks can also increase depending on the quark-potential and can lead to the generation of additional new mass. The finding of an increased particle mass upon excitation suggests that when a meson is excited, depending on the type of excitation (higher spin level / greater quark distance), the increased distance between the quarks generates new mass, which is localized near the charges of the quarks and interacts with them. In this manner, the mass-charge binding energy becomes even

more important when investigating excited meson states, depending on the type of excitation. For spin excitation, this phenomenon should not occur. This phenomenon of larger mass differences between differently charged excited meson states should occur if, due to quark confinement, newly generated mass is produced e.g. in the form of seaquarks or virtual quarks near the gluons between the constituent quarks.

V. Further investigating the D- mesons:

An examination of the D mesons shows that this materialization of mass between quarks can occur in excited states; however, it appears as if this phenomenon may not necessarily occur in all cases of excitation. For example, in the case of spin excitation, no additional mass generation should occur, and subsequently, no additional mass-charge binding energy should be generated.

For the ground level of the D0 and D+ mesons, the difference in mass is only approximately 5 MeV. For the excited state D0(2400), the difference in mass between the D0 and D+ meson is approximately 85 MeV, while for the D(2420) and D2(2460) mesons, this difference is only approximately 2 MeV. Therefore, it appears as if for the 2400 D mesons, a distance excitation occurs, while for the 2460 mesons, the excitation appears to be a spin excitation. For spin excitations, the mass-charge binding energy present in a meson should not change during excitation. These types of excitations and the resulting spectra are already well understood and are in line with the current QCD theory. The theory provided here may provide an explanation for those excitation states that are currently unexplained. These explanations state that, for example, the D0(2400) mesons are thereby characterized by an extraordinarily large difference between two differently charged forms of a single meson and/or have an extraordinarily low mass. In each case, species with an extraordinarily low mass could be explained by additionally considering the mass-charge binding energy because this energy decreases the mass of the resulting particle.

VI. Bi-modal distribution

A non-constant materialization of mass between the quarks could also explain the experimentally observed bi-modal distributions of the masses of several excited meson states, such as those of the D*2(2460)+ and D(2750) mesons. In this case, one peak would represent the meson without mass materialization in the form of seaquarks in between the existing quarks, and the other peak would represent the meson with an additional quark. With the additional working mass-charge binding energy, in these cases, the resulting mass should be significantly reduced.

VII. Quantum overlay

The zero pion and the eta and eta' mesons also show that the quantum mechanical overlay of different quarks in forming a particle will lead to a reduction in the resulting mass. This reduction in mass is greater if more particles are quantum-mechanically overlaid. Therefore, it appears that all overlaid particles are involved in the resulting total amount of charge (and the current mass of the constituent quarks) of the resulting particle. In general, the masses predicted by the current QCD theory should be slightly higher than the experimentally

observed values because the mass-charge binding energy has not been considered to date. Furthermore, this energy will lead to a minimal reduction in the resulting energy.

VIII. $1/r$ - nature of the mass-charge binding energy

In contrast, for the ground state of a meson, the quark current masses primarily interact with the quark charges. Because the quark itself also increases in radius with an increasing mass of this particular quark, the resulting mass-charge binding energy also decreases with $1/r$ for the ground state; however, this energy will still be present, as can be observed for the B^0 / B^+ mesons. In the excited state, however, the influence of the mass-charge binding energy can increase. The higher the excitation state, the more mass that is produced between the quarks and, in turn, the greater the influence of the mass-charge binding energy. An explanation for this observation can be provided if the binding energy between the quarks in the ground state does not primarily materialize in a certain location between the quarks but in the same amount equally within both quarks of the meson such that they both increase in mass. However, for the excited state, the excitation energy appears to materialize primarily in the virtual quarks located at the gluons between the quarks. In this case, if the distance between the quarks increases, the mass will increase due to the quark potential, and in turn, the mass-charge binding energy will decrease the mass of the resulting particle. Therefore, it appears that virtual quarks (seequarks) may also carry mass, at least in the excited mesons.

IX. Experimental Verification

The following method was used to verify the accuracy of the predictions, the following calculations were performed. The potential according to equation (1) was calculated for different baryons and mesons. Thus, the equation was set up with the radius defined as the unknown x and with the mass of each particle according to the data from the particle data group² as the result of the equation. The equations were then solved using an algorithm (see appendix basic program 1), which is shown in the appendix. The results are presented in table 1. The radii for differently charged particles of the same species are located at specific values. The radii for particles from different species increase with the mass of the heaviest contained quark. **Table 1** also shows how the radii can be reduced by division through the smallest radius. The radii of mesons and baryons were reduced to multiples of the smallest length. The radius was assumed to be larger for particles containing slightly heavier quarks. One explanation for this phenomenon may be the spin-spin interactions influencing the energy calculations. Several different theories and equations have been put forth for the spin-spin interaction. The simplest equation states that the interaction is the product of a constant, a spin operator for the spin of the first quark, and a spin operator for the spin of the second quark divided by the product of the masses of the two quarks³ (equation 1b). In this equation, the mass of the quark is in the denominator and thus reduces the resulting particle energy. The quark potential calculation shows that a larger radius is connected to a larger particle energy, so the energy (or mass) of the particle can be partly explained by the spin-spin interaction according to Heaton-Burgess³; therefore, this energy reduces the particle radius necessary to explain the total energy of the particle given by its mass. Because a portion of the particle energy is derived from the spin-spin interaction, only a slightly smaller amount of energy must be generated through the quark potential. Thus, by including spin-spin interactions, like particles clustered at similar radii or within a few multiples of the radii. This approach was attempted for the baryons by fixing the radius at $r =$

0.87 fm. Results are shown in **table 2**. For these calculations, the algorithm in basic program 2 (see appendix, basic program 2) was used. The spin-spin interaction is valuable for calculating the baryon and meson masses; however, energy calculations based on this spin-spin interaction for each baryon and meson species have to consider the mathematical form of the interaction. The influence of the spin-spin interaction diminishes with the mass of the constituent quarks of the meson and/or baryon. Therefore the spin-spin interaction is important mainly for the light mesons and baryons.

In the subsequent considerations the radius of the baryons was fixed to $r = 0.87$ fm.

from equation (1) follows formula (9):

$$m = \sum m_i + \Delta M_{ss} - \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{M|Q|}{0.87 \text{ fm}} - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{0.87 \text{ fm}} + k \cdot 0.87 \text{ fm} + E_R \quad (9)$$

In this equation E_R is considered to be the "residual- potential". Thereby the residual or rest-potential describes an up until now unknown form of energy.

X. Residual potential

The total energy (or mass) of the particle thus is calculated from the sum of its current quark masses, the mass- charge- binding- energy, the quark potential (according to the Cornell description), the spin-spin- potential and the "residual- potential". Thereby the mass- charge-binding- energy reduces the total mass. The quark- potential given by the Cornell description increases with an increasing radius. The spin- spin- potential reduces the total energy for particles with a spin of 1/2 and increases it for particles with a spin of 3/2. The residual- potential increases obviously with an increasing quark mass.

It thus might include a linearly increasing term with the quark mass. Also evident when looking at the Lambda and Sigma-zero particle, the flavor symmetry of the constituent quarks obviously has an effect on the total energy of the particle. This energy form will be named isospin energy (ISE) or symmetry energy in the following (for a calculation see **table 3**).

The linearly with the quark- mass increasing fraction probably should be related to the kinetic energy of the quarks in the particles and should predominantly consist of rotational energy. Further more it should be linked to the self- energy of the quarks and gluons. Accordingly, the residual energy is calculated primarily as sum of the kinetic energy, of the rotational energy and of the self- energy of the quarks. The linearity of the kinetic energy with the quark mass also causes that the constituent- quark- model is so successful. In this model the residual energy is equally distributed among the quarks.

In **figure 1** the residual potential is drawn versus the baryon particle mass and a logarithmic function of the form of Eq.10 can be seen.

$$M / E_R = 0.3633 \cdot \ln(M) - 1.0746 \quad (10)$$

Thereby the logarithmic function probably derives from the self- energy. The self- energy seems to be the inverse effect of the interaction of a beta- particle with matter electrons (compare Demröter⁴ page 88). This interaction is in principle described by the same logarithmic function.

Figure 1 M/E_R Baryons

Further more also the isopin energy can be analyzed by looking at the baryons which are isospin isomers. This is done in **table 3** and shown in **figure 2**. Interestingly a very similar logarithmic function shows up indicating that the isopin energy might be related to a different coupling constant of the self- energy of the interacting quarks. Further more it is interesting, that the logarithmic function given here for the residual potential has the form of a Green function

$$E = E^0 + 2.5 \cdot E^0 / (\ln E^0 - 1) \quad (11) \quad \text{with } E \propto G \quad (12)$$

This can also be written as

$$E = E^0 + 2.5 E^0 / \int (1/E) dE - 1) \quad (13)$$

with $G^0 \sum G \propto E^0 / \ln Z$ and $Z \propto E^0$ (14)

Takada^{5,6} et al. also favourite a beginning using reciprocal functions for describing particles self-energy. Therefore there is some theoretical background for using such a function for the description of particles self-energy^{5,6}.

Figure 2

Isopin Energy dependency on current quark mass

XI. For an explanation of the electron and quark rest masses

The classical self-energy of an electron starts from

$$mc^2 = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{q_e^2}{R} \quad (16)$$

and leads us to

$$mc^2 = \int_0^s QE(s)ds = Q \int_0^s \frac{1}{r} \rho_0 e^{-r} ds = Q \frac{1}{s} \rho_0 e^{-s} \quad (17)$$

Further more we have to account the radius dependency of the electrostatic potential of an elementary particle, which is on one hand a string

$$\varphi(r) = -\frac{\lambda}{2\pi\epsilon_0} \cdot \ln \frac{r}{R} \quad (18)$$

and on the other hand a sphere

$$\varphi(r) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \cdot \frac{q}{r} \quad (19)$$

Therefore we additionally make the ansatz:

$$-\frac{\lambda}{2\pi\epsilon_0} \cdot \ln \frac{1}{R} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \cdot \frac{q}{r} \quad (20)$$

$$\text{or } \ln R = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{q}{r} \quad (21)$$

Keeping the classical self-energy beginning leads to

$$mc^2 = q \cdot E(R) \cdot R = q_e \cdot e^{\frac{1}{2} \frac{q_e}{r}} e^{-\frac{2}{3}} \quad (22)$$

This leads us to

$$\ln(mc^2) = \left(q_e \cdot N - \frac{2}{3} \right) \quad (23)$$

with N=0,2,3 for the leptons (electron N=0) and to

$$\ln(mc^2) = \left(\frac{1}{6} \cdot q_e^2 \cdot N + 1 \right) \quad (24)$$

with N=0,1,3,5,6,9 for the quarks.

Thereby N is the quantum number representing the reciprocal radius r of the elementary particle. In case of a quark we get the second power of the charge above all because of the

confinement, the electrostatic interaction always acts between three quarks. We get the same result, if we start from Greens function

$$E = E^0 + 2.5E^0 / (\ln E^0 - 1) \quad (11)$$

and relate the rest energy E^0 to the rest mass- term mc^2 and E to the electrostatic potential

$$\varphi(R) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{q_e^2}{R} \quad (25)$$

followed by $R \rightarrow 1/N$ with N being the quantum number again.

References

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Tables and Figures

Table 1

The radii were calculated according to the algorithm in basic program 1 (see appendix). Quark- masses, mass- charge- binding- energy, and quark- potential are considered. Different particles from the species were found to be focused on the same radius.

Partikel	Quark	Masse	Radius [fm] calculated	Radius [fm] exper. / lit.	div by 0.14fm	div by 0.931fm
p	uud	938.272	0.931	0.87		1
n	udd	939.565	0.93	0.86		1
Λ^0	uds	1115.6	1.04			1.1
Σ^+	uus	1189.4	1.12			1.2
Σ^0	uds	1192.6	1.11			1.2
Σ^-	dds	1197.4	1.11			1.2
Ξ^0	uss	1314.9	1.16			1.2
Ξ^-	dss	1321.3	1.16			1.2
Λ_c	udc	2286.46	1.39			1.5
Ω^-	sss	1672.45	1.42			1.5
Ξ_c^0	dsc	2471	1.42			1.5
Ξ_c^+	usc	2467	1.47			1.5
Ω_c^0	ssc	2697.5	1.54			1.6
Ξ_{cc}^+	ccd	3519	1.62			1.7
Ω_b^-	ssb	6054	1.85			2
π	du	139.56	0.14		1	
K^+	us	493.65	0.448		3	
K^0	ds	497.67	0.433		3	
D^+	cd	1869	0.9356		6	1
D^0	cu	1865	1		7	1
D_s	cs	1969	0.95		7	1
B^+	ub	5279.1	1.7		12	
B^0	db	5279.5	1.53		11	
B_s	bs	5415	1.28		9	
η	cc	2979	1.16		8	

Table 1 radii calculated according to basic program 1 (see appendix). Quark- masses. mass-charge- binding- energy. and quark- potential are considered. If a further energy form (self-energy) is additionally considered substantially smaller radii are resulting.

$$\Delta M_{SS} = a \cdot \frac{S_q S_q}{m_q m_q}$$

Table 2

The radii and spin-spin potentials were calculated according to basic program 2 (see appendix). The quark masses, mass-charge binding energy, quark potential and spin-spin interactions were included. The spin- spin- interactions were calculated as $\Delta M_{ss} = a \cdot \frac{\sigma_{q1}\sigma_{q2}}{m_{q1}m_{q2}}$.

The smallest baryon- radius, which is the radius of the nucleon, was used as the universal radius for all of the baryons. If different radii were allowed for the different baryon species, then this could cause additional spin-spin potentials. Indeed, the results show that different particles of the same species have spin-spin potentials within the same range, while particles from different species have different spin-spin potentials.

Partikel	Quark	Masse	Radius [fm] calculated	Radius [fm] exper. / lit.	ΔM_{ss} [MeV] potential $\sigma_1\sigma_2$	E_R [MeV]
p	uud	938.272	0.87	0.87	-8.6	70.6
n	udd	939.565	0.87	0.86	-8.6	70.6
Λ^0	uds	1115.6	0.87		-3.1	181.1
Σ^+	uus	1189.4	0.87		-3.1	265
Σ^0	uds	1192.6	0.87		-3.1	258
Σ^-	dds	1197.4	0.87		-3.1	252
Ξ^0	uss	1314.9	0.87		-0.2	317
Ξ^-	dss	1321.3	0.87		-0.2	304
Λ_c	udc	2286.46	0.87			750
Ω^-	sss	1672.45	0.87			586
Ξ_c^0	dsc	2471	0.87			752
Ξ_c^+	usc	2467	0.87			880
Ω_c^0	ssc	2697.5	0.87			919
Ξ_{cc}^+	ccd	3519	0.87			1323.5
Ω_b^-	ssb	6054	0.87			2054
π	du	139.56	0.14			0
K^+	us	493.65	0.14			261
K^0	ds	497.67	0.14			261
D^+	cd	1869	0.14			601
D^0	cu	1865	0.14			646
D_s	cs	1969	0.14			615
B^+	ub	5279.1	0.14			1425
B^0	db	5279.5	0.14			1266
B_s	bs	5415	0.14			1312
η	cc	2979	0.14			

Table 2 radii calculated according to program 2. Quark- masses (1), mass- charge- binding- energy for baryons 0.25mq/r and for mesons 0.016mq/r (2), quark- potential 1GeV/fm(3) and spin- spin- interactions (4) are considered. Spin- spin- interactions are considered according to

$$\Delta M_{ss} = a \cdot \frac{\sigma_{q1}\sigma_{q2}}{m_{q1}m_{q2}} = -46\text{MeV}^3/(m_1m_2).$$

Rest Energy is the residual energy part unexplained by the four energy parts. For baryons kr is considered as 1000MeV/fm, for mesons kr is considered as 252MeV/fm.

Table 3

M	quarks	particle I=0	particle mass	analog particle	particle mass	Isopin Energy
109	uds	Λ	1115	Σ^0	1192	77
1278	udc	Λ_{c^+}	2286	Σ_{c^+}	2452	166
1400	ssc	Ω	2695			
4198	udb	Λ_b	5620	Σ_b^+	5811	191
4400	ssb	Ω_b	6165			

Table 3 Analyzing the isospin energy (ISE) by looking at the isospin isomeric baryons

Figures

Figure 1 M/E_R Baryons

Figure 2

Isopin Energy dependency on current quark mass

Appendix

Programms

Basic Programm 1

```
10 input „u“;u
20 input „d“;d
30 input „c“;c
40 input „s“;s
50 input „b“;b
51 input „should be mass“;so
55 k=1000
56 alpha=0.2
60 M=4*u+4*d+1200*c+101*s+4190*b
70 L=2/3*u+1/3*d+2/3*c+1/3*s+1/3*b
73 input „estimated radius“; r
75 print „next t”
81 E= M-1/4*M*L/(r/10)-4/3*alpha/(r/10)+k*(r/10)
89 print „radius=“;r
90 print „E=“;E
91 if E=so then print „OK ready“
92 print „mass should be“;so
93 if E>so then r=r - 1
94 if E<so then r=r+1
95 if abs(s-e)<1 then end
96 print „M”;M
100 goto 75
110 end
```

Basic Programm 2

```
10 input „u“;u
20 input „d“;d
30 input „c“;c
40 input „s“;s
50 input „b“;b
51 input „should be mass“;so
55 k=1000
56 alpha=0.2
60 M=4*u+4*d+1200*c+101*s+4190*b
70 L=2/3*u+1/3*d+2/3*c+1/3*s+1/3*b
73 input „estimated radius“; r
81 E=so-( M-1/4*M*L/(8.7/10)-4/3*alpha/(8.7/10)+k*(8.7/10))
90 print „Delta Mss=“;E
92 print „mass should be“;so
110 end
```